

Perceived Challenges and Related Coping Styles Developed by Mentors in Formal Youth Mentoring Relationships

Abstract: This paper discusses the characteristics of coping styles that are developed to deal with perceived mentoring challenges during mentors' experiences in formal youth mentoring bonds. Data is drawn from an extensive study on mentoring relational processes conducted in the Czech youth mentoring programme Big Brothers Big Sisters/Pět P between 2010 and 2017. In-depth semi-structured interviews with ten mentoring matches were conducted three times over one year of mentoring involvement. Qualitative Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) focused on mentors' experiences and perceptions when occupying a mentoring role, and the subsequent relational characteristics and dynamics of the ten mentoring bonds. The reported results contribute to the theory on formal and natural mentoring relationships in a child-and-youth-centred perspective and address gaps in the knowledge on good evidence-based practice in formal youth mentoring interventions.

Keywords: Youth mentoring, quality in mentoring interventions, mentor experience, mentor approach, autonomy support

1. Introduction

Mentoring relationships are developmental intergenerational bonds between children or youth (mentees) and their significant non-parental adults (mentors). Mentoring is commonly defined as an asymmetrical, yet reciprocal, at-will relationship in which the mentors share their knowledge and experience with the mentees and support the mentees' optimal development and well-being (Rhodes, 2005). The principles of natural mentoring are implemented in youth mentoring interventions, programmes and social services for children and young people in different target groups. Formal mentoring relationships aim to contribute to positive behavioural, relational and academic outcomes in young people (Raposa et al., 2019; Dubois & Keller, 2017; McQuillin et al., 2013). Although empirical evidence supports the thesis that mentoring programmes are effective across a range of developmental outcomes, meta-analyses of mentoring programmes have

consistently shown that the positive effects of formal mentoring are typically only minor, or even lacking (Christensen et al., 2020; Raposa et al., 2019; Herrera et al., 2013; DuBois et al., 2011). Indeed, formal mentoring bonds have been identified in the research as having different resulting qualities and benefits for recipients than developmental and prescriptive bonds (Morrow and Styles, 1995; Brumovská & Malkova, 2010; Karcher et al., 2010; Brady & Brumovská, 2017). This paper argues that the quality of the mentoring relationship is a critical component of formal youth mentoring programmes and their benefits for mentees (Chesmore et al., 2017; Pryce & Keller, 2012).

The literature argues that the mentor's approach to the relationship and interactions with mentees is a crucial feature that impacts the relational dynamics and quality (Raposa et al., 2016; Brumovská, 2017). Individual features identified in mentors' approach, such as mentors' attitudes (Karcher et al., 2010), their unrealistic expectations concerning the time and nature of the relationship and the mentoring role (Grossman and Rhodes, 2002; Spencer, 2007b), perceived discrepancies between the role mentors expected and the role they experienced (Madia and Lutz, 2004), their perceived self-efficacy, and their positive a priori motivation (Spencer et al., 2017, Karcher et al., 2005) affected the relational characteristics and dynamics, and the level of benefits received by mentees, and thus impacted on the resulted effects of the mentoring intervention.

Positively perceived mentors were identified as playing a semi-parental role in which they functioned as role models for their protégés (Dallos and Comley-Ross, 2005). Mentors were described by mentees as surprisingly interesting and kind from their first impressions, as overcoming mentees' negative expectations quickly, and as accepting mentees on their terms and valuing and empowering their capabilities and abilities. The latter trait was received positively by mentees as giving them a sense of being valuable and significant people. An empathetic, youth-centred approach was experienced as mentors sensitively understanding the mentees and their personality, character, interests and needs (Spencer, 2006; Thomson & Zand, 2010).

In terms of relational dynamics, young people specifically valued experiences of trust, control, reciprocity, fun and sharing as elements of mentoring bonds (Spencer and Liang, 2009). Mentors were also perceived as honest in their advice and as reliable, available, respectful and engaged in the relationship. Mentors supported young people by listening to their concerns and offering validation, feedback, suggestions and acceptance (Dallos and Comley-Ross, 2005; Spencer and Liang, 2009). Companionship and collaboration were ways in which mentors offered encouragement and practi-

cal, instrumental support on the secure basis of the relationship (Spencer, 2006). Reciprocity was experienced as a simple form of exchange that fostered mentees' self-respect and made mentoring experiences positive. Mentors' ability to listen and respond with honesty, offering genuine feedback and opinions without passing judgement on the mentees for their decisions, made the emotional support they provided beneficial (Dallos and Comley-Ross, 2005). Negotiation over shared activities and experiencing the "fun factor" while generally enjoying activities were associated with a positive mentoring bond (Spencer and Liang, 2009). As a result, mentees experienced trust and mutual openness and believed that mentors cared for them, understood them and knew them.

On the other hand, formal youth mentoring relationships can impose risks on its recipients; vulnerable children and young people. Morrow and Styles (1995) identified Prescriptive formal mentoring bonds with the features of a risky mentoring approach. In these helping relationships, youths did not have a voice in determining the types of mentoring activities, while the mentors primarily intended to fulfil the goals they set: they pushed children to achieve, did not pay attention to their needs, and were not alert to their personalities and wishes. The children tended to withdraw and terminate their involvement prematurely. Colley (2003) discussed how mentors in the British empowering mentoring programme were judgemental and prescriptive to young people in their approach, rather than empowering. Spencer (2007b) identified the risk factors that reduced the quality of mentoring bonds. Rhodes et al. (2009) discussed the ethical issues of formal mentoring and its risks in rather general terms, igniting the discussion on mentoring ethics.

Nevertheless, as reflected in the literature review, the knowledge on formal mentoring principles still presents gaps regarding relational characteristics and dynamics. For instance, none of the studies in the field explored how mentors perceived mentoring challenges and subsequently coped with them from an early stage, or how their approach when dealing with perceived mentoring challenges subsequently impacted the relational dynamics and quality of the formal mentoring bond.

This paper aims to show what mentors perceived as challenging about their mentoring role and their mentees; and how mentors coped with the challenges they perceived in children's behaviour while building the mentoring bond, addressing the questions: 1. What are the perceived challenges in the mentoring role identified by mentors in formal youth mentoring relationships? 2. What style did mentors develop and apply to cope with perceived challenges?

1.1 Methodology

This paper reports partial results of an extensive longitudinal, qualitative tracking study on the relational features of mentoring with in-depth phenomenological interviews (Kvale, 1996) and IPA (interpretative phenomenological analysis). The QSR NVivo 10 software was used to examine how mentors make sense of their experiences in formal youth mentoring relationships over one year of their involvement (Smith et al., 2009).

1.2 Research design

The fieldwork took place in two mentoring affiliates of the Big Brothers Big Sisters CZ/Pět P (BBBS CZ) mentoring programme in the Czech Republic in urban settings between 2010 and 2012. At the time, the BBBS CZ programme operated through 20 affiliates. BBBS CZ recruited, trained, matched, and supervised mentoring matches in line with Big Brothers Big Sisters International standards of practice. All new mentoring matches, comprising volunteers, children, and parents, agreed to participate in the programme for at least ten continuous months.

The research study was explained to all newly trained mentors (potential participants) in autumn 2010 through oral presentations and information sheets. Participants provided written consent. Caseworkers informed newly matched parents and children about the research study via verbal presentations and written information sheets. Out of all potential participants, 10 mentoring matches comprising volunteers, children and youth and their parents agreed to take part in the study interviews over the next 12 months of their involvement and were selected purposively as participants¹.

1.3 Research sample

There were 10 volunteer mentors (8 female, 2 male): high-school students (1), college students (4), or employed (5), all between 18 and 28 years of age. The 10 mentees were six girls and four boys between 6 and 15 years of age;

1 Due to its idiographic focus, the IPA approach explores similarities and differences in people's experiences of phenomena, comparing cases in detail. It thus aims to find a relatively small and homogeneous sample (Smith et al., 2012). The sample was homogeneous in that all the research participants had experienced mentoring in the BBBS CZ programme, though in different roles.

all were Caucasian and of Czech origin. Professionals identified them as children with various additional needs who could benefit from mentoring support. They had socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds, were in institutional care, were diagnosed with ADHD, had health difficulties, or experienced issues of exclusion from their peers, such as bullying at school. They were referred to the BBBS CZ services by school psychologists, educational support workers, GPs, special pedagogues, or psychiatrists.

1.4 Data collection method

In-depth semi-structured interviews lasting 20–75 minutes were conducted with 10 mentors and mentees² during the first month and after 5 and 8 months of the mentoring experience. The first round explored their initial motivations for taking part, their expectations, understanding of the roles, and initial experiences, and their perceptions of mentoring relationships. The second and third interviews explored their reflections on their involvement, experiences, perceived satisfaction and benefits, the mentors' approach to children, and relational dynamics. Ten parents/carers were interviewed twice: once during the first month and once after 8 months. Parents reflected on their experiences with the programme, their perceptions of their child's mentor, and the perceived satisfaction and benefits for the children.

Three caseworkers from the two branches of BBBS who regularly supervised the tracked matches provided further information once a month over the period of 12 months that helped us contextualise the matches from the programme's perspective. Together, the data collection process yielded 30

2 Interviews with 10 mentees were conducted at the same time as the mentors' interviews, examining the mentees' experiences of the mentoring meetings and their perception of the mentors. Interviews with children and young people – respondents who ranged between 6 and 15 years of age – were adjusted based on a child-and-youth-centred approach to interviewing, using play or arts-based methods associated with mentors and mentoring experiences. They talked on the interview topics during the play activity. Arts-based tools were also used to introduce the theme of mentoring experiences, e.g., children drew and told stories about their mentors based on a picture of a mentor. These interviews were part of the case studies analysis in the earliest stages of IPA analysis. The results of these interviews are implicitly present in the research results in the overview on the relational processes and interactions, as presented in the research results. This paper, however, reports on the data on the mentors' interviews only.

interviews with 10 mentors, 30 with 10 children, 24 with parents, and 6 interviews with 3 caseworkers from BBBS CZ.

1.5 Data analysis

The data analysis process followed the iterative cycles of IPA as described by Smith et al. (2009). This process began by listening to the recordings and verbatim transcriptions and anonymising all the interviews. It proceeded with careful inductive analysis of each of the 10 cases (consisting of the 10 participating mentoring matches) before moving on to cross-case comparison and the refinement of those themes in mentors' experiences (interviews) that were relevant to the research question. The QSR NVivo 10 analytical software was used for the analysis. This process is schematically outlined in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1 – The Seven Steps Of IPA Data Analysis (by Charlick, McKellar, Fielder & Pincombe, 2015; adapted from Smith et al., 2009)

At the final stages (points 5, 6 and 7), the data for further analysis were reduced to the mentors' experiences and perspectives in the mentoring role only. As a result, ten themes were identified from mentors' experiences and perspectives that were common to all mentoring relationships, and these were further compared between cases. Two types of mentoring relation-

ships with similar shared experiences and related relational characteristics and dynamics were reported in detail as the study results. The results were discussed from the perspective of Self-Determination Theory (SDT, Ryan and Deci, 1985) as autonomy-controlling and autonomy-supportive mentoring relationships (Ryan & Solky, 1996; Weinstein & Ryan, 2010).

1.6 Results of the study

This paper compares the themes of 1. Perceived mentoring challenges in mentors' experience, and 2. Style of coping with the perceived challenges, by mentors' approach to children. The reported themes are further compared between mentors with 1. Initial controlling motivations (hereafter CMs) and 2. Initial autonomous motivations (hereafter AMs) (Brumovská & Brady, 2021).

The results identified 1. perceived challenges in the mentoring role and 2. features in mentors' limit-setting styles when coping with perceived challenging behaviour in mentees, encountered in the mentoring interactions.

The developed styles of coping with the perceived challenges differed depending on the initial CM (n=6) or AM (n=4) for taking part in the mentoring.

2. Perceived mentoring challenges

All mentors found it challenging to seek the children's acceptance in the relationship while at the same time wanting to feel secure and comfortable in the mentoring role. They described their experiences of mentoring challenges as follows:

2.1 Challenge when negotiating children's behaviour: negative expectations or acceptance of mentee's character & behaviour

All mentors were informed in brief about the future mentees' profiles by the mentoring programme. Following that, they reflected the challenges in children perceived both, while working with children or as challenges in children's profiles that referred them to the mentoring programme. The first

identified challenge of the mentoring role thus concerned the mentors' expectations regarding the children's character or behaviour.

Three mentors with initial CMs formed negative or concrete expectations about the mentees and their behaviour before the mentoring meetings started, based upon the information they received about the mentees and their background from caseworkers.

L: They told me she likes to keep things that she doesn't own because she just likes them ... she would not take anything in a shop but here (place specified) where she feels safe she might just take something and keep it. So, I think we will come across that at some point. (Luisa, January 2011).

At the same time, they had to cope with the challenging emotions arising from the discrepancy between their expectations and their actual different and/or positive experiences of children in the first mentoring meetings:

M: Firstly, I was worried as I was told before I met her that she lived in a special children's institution ... so I was quite worried about what kind of a kid she is, what kind of issues she might have but I realised that she was grand, she had friends, and I didn't see any issue with her at first sight ...

(Marta, February 2011).

The discrepancy between mentors' expectations and the different lived experience of the mentoring meetings with the mentee subsequently presented another challenge for the mentors to cope with from the outset of the mentoring meetings:

M: she is well-behaved, brought up well ... she has a similar world perspective, she is compassionate I thought she would be like ... lack the basic rules. But I see that she has a sense of morality. She does not cheat; she would never steal anything ... it looks like she is from an uncomplicated family but she's not because she's here (in the programme). It is quite a contradiction for me. I don't know what to think of it (Marta, February 2011).

On the other hand, mentors with initial AMs similarly had to cope with the mentees' challenging behaviour. For instance, they described it as a challenge to cope with children's lack of interest during mentoring meetings and search for mutuality in mentoring interactions:

T: once or twice when I picked him up at school, we walked together, and he was quiet so I asked him what's the matter and he replied nothing and then he started to talk ...

R: ... and is there something he wouldn't share with you?

T: well ... sometimes he's not very keen on doing anything ... I can suggest ten different options on what we could do together, and he doesn't agree with anything and says no to everything and just wants to go home ... so these are probably the only ones (challenges) but nothing major, anyway

(Tina, December 2011)

Nevertheless, autonomously motivated mentors did not feel discouraged, confused, frustrated, challenged, tense, demotivated, or offended by the expressions of children's challenging behaviour. Instead, they understood these features to be part of the child's nature and accepted them. As such, they responded to this kind of children's behaviour with empathy and understanding:

T: he is this way sometimes when he doesn't feel like talking, he expresses himself with this that he doesn't talk much, and when I ask him, he replies in one word or not at all ... but I think I know when he's this way and it's not often, anyway ...

(Tina, June 2011)

In general, mentors with initial AMs recognised mentoring challenges in advance of the mentoring meetings. At the same time, they reflected on their skills for the mentoring role, and their intention to develop a mentoring role congruent with these skills to feel comfortable, even when it was necessary to limit mentees' challenging behaviour.

For instance, Ivan perceived that being authentic as well as accepting mentees and their behaviour was essential for coping with the perceived challenges in the child's behaviour,

I: I chose the programme (BBBS) because there's nothing to fail ... because your aim is just to be yourself, to be a good friend for the child so you don't have to pretend anything, you don't need any special skills ... it is a very usual kind of work based on one-to-one (interactions), so it's easy ... you are as you are ... and that's the best thing (you can do) ... (Ivan, January 2011)

2.2 Challenge in negotiation of relational boundaries: loose or secure emotional bond

Two mentors with initial CMs and two mentors with initial AMs identified a challenge in establishing emotional boundaries in the relationship that would be beneficial for the child and comfortable for mentors.

Mentors with CMs described how they were challenged by the intense emotional experiences in relationships with children. For instance, Viki experienced the challenge of extreme emotional openness by her mentee during the first mentoring meeting. On the one hand, she appreciated and felt flattered that the child entrusted her and shared his issues. At the same time, she felt overwhelmed by the intensity and timing of his emotional openness in the mentoring bond. She felt that this openness was potentially unhealthy for both the mentee and herself:

V: ... He started to be open on the very first meeting we had ... I didn't expect he would be so open on the very first meeting ... that he would tell me that so early ... I wanted to leave it for later when we knew each other better ... but I am happy for it because I am pleased he did it, and I know that he can be open with me with other issues as well, he will know I accept him, and he can tell me things (Viki, January 2011)

Similarly, Kveta's relationship was also challenging in terms of negotiating the emotional boundaries from the outset of the mentoring meetings. The child expressed initial emotional openness and intense attachment, which Kveta tolerated and even reinforced in a close emotional interaction without setting limits. She argued that the child needed her in this mentoring bond she supported and considered beneficial for the mentee. At the same time, she spoke of her worries that the child could become emotionally too close and dependent:

K: I was worried in the beginning ... that she could be bonded with me too closely and act like I was her foster mother ... we arranged the meetings within a short period ... we chatted together, and the personal contact has been much closer between us, she needs to cuddle, she needs to stroke, she initiates it on her own ... you could see that they don't receive enough love and care from their mums ... (Květa, January 2011)

Despite the emotional challenge they reflected upon, neither Viki nor Kveta intended to actively set relational boundaries with clear limits for their mentees. Instead, the discrepancy between the description of the mentors' experience (overwhelming) and their interpretation of these events (it was good it happened) is evident from the outset of the involvement. It is the beginning of the dynamics that developed further (cf. Brumovská, 2017).

Like controlling mentors, autonomously motivated mentors were challenged by the need to establish secure relational boundaries to combat uncomfortable feelings they perceived and recognised in the mentoring role. Contrary to mentors with CMs, however, autonomously motivated mentors described the experience of challenges in relational boundaries connected to their initial AMs to enjoy the mentoring experiences with their mentees; their reflection and recognition of the limits in their mentoring skills; and conscious acceptance of responsibility for coping with the perceived mentoring challenge actively, using the mentoring competencies they consciously 'owned'. Subsequently, they reflected on and acknowledged their active mentoring skill of coping with the identified mentoring challenge – and felt competent to cope with it. Importantly, this process occurred before the meetings with children started, during the mentors' initial training.

For instance, Sára mentioned that the challenges she perceived were like those of controlling mentors. However, she explained how she coped with the challenges by actively reflecting on her mentoring skills, actively employing her responsibility to develop authentic communication with the child and inform her mentee about her boundaries in the mentoring bond. Importantly, she found and accepted her limits in the mentoring role following her active contemplation of the perceived mentoring challenge:

S: ... I had worries whether ... he could become very dependent on me ... and I would have issues finishing the relationship ... also the challenge could be if he'd gone too hyper to set up control over him so he wouldn't be too much ...

... and it was essential for me to admit that I don't have to do everything the child wants from me ... it was a ground-breaking point for me to realise it, that just telling him: "Don't do this because ... I don't like it" ... to realise that it is up to me to find my boundaries and admit to myself what is OK and what is not OK and then make him feel that too somehow I think it is kind of my own responsibility ... I don't do everything the other person wants me to do but find some kind of my limits and just give it to him too ... and I feel I am easy with it now.

(Sára, January 2011)

Similarly, Nina described how she identified a challenge of establishing secure relational boundaries; she worried that she could become overprotective of her new mentee. At the same time, as she actively reflected on her mentoring skills and limits, she concluded that, as a mentor, she could only be suited to a child without the issues that triggered her overprotective approach. Thus, she accepted the responsibility to actively resolve her perceived mentoring challenge by finding and articulating her boundaries in the mentoring role during the matching with her future mentee. Subsequently, she had positive expectations about her future mentoring role:

N: I probably went into it quite light-heartedly ... but when I heard the cases of clients, their background and their issues ... I realised I would probably feel very sorry for them, everything they had to experience and stuff ... so I was bit worried that if I got such a child ... I think it would be evident in my approach to them in a way ... I would probably tend to be overprotective of them ... but it didn't scare me ... instead I became more curious and started to think about it more ...

(Nina, December 2011)

2.3 Challenge of negotiation of responsibility: self-sacrifice or authentic approach in the mentoring role

Mentors were challenged by how to negotiate the perceived responsibility in the mentoring role in a way that would be beneficial for the child and at the same time enjoyable for mentors. Again, they differed according to their initial motivations in the way they dealt with their perceived responsibility in the role. Mentors with initial CMs encountered and dealt with the perceived challenge in their interactions with children, whereas mentors with AMs identified, reflected, and resolved perceived challenges in line with the mentoring skills they felt competent with in advance of the mentoring meetings.

Two mentors with initial CMs described their acceptance of children in terms of initial positive involvement and emotional availability for the meetings with the children, while they were willing to include activities of the mentees' choice to foster enjoyment. Nevertheless, as they felt responsible for mentees' needs and well-being, they expressed the challenging feelings of the sacrifice of their enjoyment they perceived as necessary to meet the mentee's needs. To fulfil their perceived role responsibly and be helpful to the mentee, they thought they needed to sacrifice the enjoyment of their mentoring role:

M: ... he wants to go to see the hockey which I don't particularly fancy but would put up with it for him for sure ... and as I promised that we will do arts & crafts with the candlesticks ... I wouldn't cancel the meeting even if I felt very sick now ...

(Matylda, January 2011)

Mentors with initial AMs also found their responsibility for the child a challenging part of the relationship as they felt it could limit their authenticity and enjoyment in the mentoring role, or they were worried about their ability to cope with their responsibility for the child. However, they described how they balanced their responsibility in the mentoring role with the recognition that finding mutual enjoyment in the friendly relationship was a natural part of the mentoring bond and thus a goal of their approach following their initial AMs:

S: I initially thought that a volunteer is supposed to direct the child ... that a mentor supports the family if it is not working ... so I would be bringing the child up ... however, I realised that it is much less responsible ... I am not his mum, and we can have fun together ... he'd be my friend like anyone else ...

(Sara, June 2011)

3. Coping with perceived mentoring challenges

Mentors differed significantly in the way they coped with challenges depending on the two identified types of motivation.

3.1 Coping with control of children's autonomy and behaviour: implicit expectations regarding mentees' behaviour

Mentors with initial CMs created implicit high expectations but did not communicate them clearly to mentees. This approach to perceived challenges in the child's behaviour subsequently led to frustration in the mentoring role and dissatisfaction with the mentoring relationship (cf. Bru-movská, 2017).

For instance, Luisa showed how the child's manner of communication, interests, and needs clashed with her expectations of the child's behaviour and her ability to communicate her boundaries openly and authentically. As

such, the dynamics of conflict and her frustration in the mentoring role were developed from the outset:

*L: ... she says she is hungry, and she'd like to eat but she won't ask you: "Would you give me something? Would you maybe pay for me?" ... or she could ask me to lend her money even though it's clear she wouldn't pay it back ... she doesn't do this ... she just comes and says: "I am hungry" And she waits to see what will happen. Just like that ... I take it almost as blackmailing from her
(Luisa, January 2011)*

3.2 Coping with control of children's autonomy and behaviour: expectations regarding children's compliance, obedience and passivity

In the coping style of mentors with initial CMs, a link was also found between children's compliance with mentors' expectations about behaviour, on one hand, and whether mentors viewed involvement in the mentoring bond as positive and rewarding, on the other. Mentors intended to limit the repeated occurrence of the perceived mentoring challenges by expressing positive regard for mentees' obedience (cf. Deci et al., 1994). They emphasised and supported the children's compliant nature and passivity, rewarding them with positive involvement and feedback when mentees complied with their expectations:

V: I clicked with him especially because ... he's so shy ... when I first saw him sitting there kind of worried, holding back in the chair, I thought he'd be nice ... thanks to him being very appreciative, it is not necessary to kind of run around him and organise sophisticated activities to fascinate him ... I think he is rather humble, he appreciates a little ... I think he will be happy with everything I propose for the activity.

T: Did you experience any conflict between you so far?

V: No, not at all, I think something will come up like that, but he might be a conformist; he might also perceive me as being older than him ... If I said something or if we had any conflict between us, he would hold back, become quiet, and not complain. He wouldn't dare. (Viki, January 2011)

3.3 Coping with children's challenging behaviour by informative limit-setting: reflection, responsibility and resolution of challenges by supporting children's autonomy

During the challenging mentoring events, mentors with initial AMs provided information and emotional feedback on mentees' challenging behaviour, followed by offering children choices regarding the subsequent actions. Thus, they supported mentees' autonomy in regulating their challenging behaviour (cf. Ryan and Solky, 1996; Deci et al., 1994; Ryan and Deci, 1985).

Limit setting with informative and emotional feedback during challenging events

Unlike controlling mentors, autonomy-supportive mentors only limited mentees' behaviour when the challenging event occurred in the mentoring interactions. In these events, mentors offered the mentee feedback on the event and the mentors' feelings and experiences triggered by the challenging event, explaining why it was challenging for them. Importantly, they felt responsible, secure and competent to inform children about these authentic feelings, even if they felt uncomfortable. Thus, they provided important information with feedback on children's challenging behaviour (Deci et al., 1994).

For instance, Ivan mentioned his willingness to be authentic with his mentee from the outset of the meetings as his approach to setting limits on a child's challenging behaviour. He accepted responsibility for providing authentic feedback to the child while informing the mentee about what he would find challenging in the mentee's behaviour – as the event happened:

I: ... I think be honest and don't pretend anything in front of the child ... when you are bothered by something he's doing, just tell him directly or on the other hand, if you are bored with something, say it honesty ... if you don't like something that the other person's doing, he doesn't know that you don't feel OK about what he's doing, so it is helpful to tell him about it immediately and then talk about it more ...

(Ivan, January and December 2011)

Sára summarised what mentors with initial AMs had in common: the feedback they provided with their feelings and attitudes was an identified tool

that mentors consciously used to place boundaries on what they perceived as challenging about children's behaviour:

S: ... I am a different role model for him to someone he has for instance at home ... I want to let him know that these are my attitudes ... I always tell him non-directly, going more like around it than telling him directly what to do ... so I am just expressing my own opinion about things ... when he sometimes comments on some things around, I don't tend to tell him: "Don't do this". But: "I wouldn't do that because ..." and it applies to many situations ...

(Sara, June 2011)

3.4 Provision of choice

Finally, supportive mentors in general did not control children's behaviour directly, but limited it by offering options the children could choose from. Ivan summarised the attitudes of supportive mentors in setting the limits on children's behaviour when he explained that his style in controlling a child's challenging behaviour involved providing information together with the option for the child to decide whether to accept the information and thus limit their behaviour accordingly – out of an autonomous motivation that is supported with this approach:

I: ... at least verbalising it could suggest to him that it wouldn't be a good way to act ... however I alone probably have little influence on whether he takes something out of it or not ...

(Ivan, December 2011)

Sara then explained how she succeeded in practice during a mentoring interaction by limiting the child's challenging behaviour. By providing a choice for the child, she set the boundary regarding the recurring challenging event:

S: ... and (I give him a choice) when we're handling money ... he doesn't have any pocket money and I also have a limited amount I can give him ... and he tends to ... you know ... they would like to have everything when they have money for it ... so he tries ... he wants this and that ... but I tell him to choose one thing only we buy for him ... and he tries to get more but he won't get more than that ...

(Sára, December 2011)

These mentors have developed a style of setting limits regarding children's challenging behaviour that supported children's autonomy with information, emotional feedback and the provision of choice (Deci et al., 1994). The so-called informative limit-setting coping style became a core dynamic of mentoring interactions from the outset. These dynamics became the baseline of the mentoring bonds that were developed and found to be beneficial in supporting mentees' autonomy, competence and other individual needs. In addition, this style of coping was one of the features that developed secure mentoring bonds featuring quality and relational satisfaction from the outset (cf. Brumovská, 2017).

Table 1: Summary of perceived mentoring challenges and coping styles of mentors in formal youth mentoring bonds: Perceived mentoring challenges and coping styles of mentors with initial controlling and autonomous motivations.

WHO?		Mentors with Initial Controlling Motivations	Mentors with Initial Autonomous Motivations
Perceived mentoring challenge	Challenge in negotiation of children's behaviour	Negative expectations/acceptance of child's behaviour Challenge of perceived discrepancy between a-priori negative expectations about mentee's behaviour/character and actual experiences with the child in mentoring interactions.	No a priori expectations on child's negative/challenging character or behaviour
	Challenge in negotiation of relational boundaries	Loose emotional bond. Relational boundaries are set-up with loose limits/regulations for mentees.	Mentors create a secure structure in boundaries of the mentoring bond
	Challenge of negotiation of responsibility the mentoring role	Tendency to self-sacrifice and sacrifice of one's satisfaction in the mentoring role for mentee's good	Authentic approach: Open and honest reflection on one's mentoring skills Recognised and accepted limits in one's mentoring skills Accepted responsibility to inform mentees honestly in line with one's recognised mentoring skills.
Coping with mentoring challenges	Coping styles features	Control of children's behaviour with prescribed implicit relational rules and expectations on mentees	Limit setting with Informative and Emotional feedback in challenging events.
		Control of autonomy with expectations on children's compliance, obedience, and passivity.	Honest and authentic information provided to mentees on mentors' uncomfortable feelings in challenging mentoring events.
	Results of mentor's approach	Control and disempowerment of children's spontaneity and authenticity	Provision of choice with child-centered approach, led by child's interests. Facilitating children's active agency, intrinsic motivation and satisfaction in the mentoring bond.

4. Discussion and recommendations

This paper reports details of mentors' experiences, identified as relating to the themes of 1. perceived mentoring challenges during mentors' experiences, and 2. Style of coping with the perceived challenges, as developed by mentors. The styles of coping with the perceived challenges, as developed by mentors, differed depending on whether mentors had initial CMs or AMs for taking part in mentoring (Brumovská & Brady, 2021). The results for mentors of these two groups are thus compared.

The results identified 1. three perceived mentoring challenges present in the nature of the mentoring role or in mentoring interactions; 2. features in the limit-setting styles mentors adopt to cope with the challenging behaviour perceived in mentees.

The experience of mentoring challenges was common to all the tracked mentors. Mentors differed, however, in the way they coped with these challenges. The resulting features identified in mentors' styles of coping with challenging events with mentees are found to be in congruence with cognitive evaluation theory (CET theory; Deci et al., 1994). Thus, CET provides an insight into the results of this study by explaining how the way mentors cope with challenging mentoring events can either support or control mentees' motivation and autonomy in the regulation of their behaviour, and subsequent satisfaction with the mentoring bond (cf. Brumovská, 2017).

Mentors who efficiently coped with mentees' challenging behaviour addressed the perceived challenges as soon as they identified them. They reflected on and accepted their responsibility to cope with the perceived challenges congruently with the recognised mentoring skills they consciously 'owned' and felt competent with from the outset of their involvement in mentoring. They also emphasised that they had an active intention to be authentic, in line with their initial autonomous motivation (Brumovská & Brady, 2021).

Subsequently, they offered mentees honest feedback with information on their behaviour and its impact on them and their feelings. Even though this feedback could be uncomfortable, mentors were also committed to informing mentees honestly about the consequences of their actions. In addition, they provided mentees with a choice regarding reactions to this type of challenging interaction.

On the other hand, mentors with initial CMs presumed that mentees would have certain challenges and tried to set limits with implicit expectations of preventing the occurrence of the challenging events.

As a result, mentors with an informative limit-setting style supported mentees' autonomous regulation of their behaviour. On the contrary, mentors who set up implicit expectations on mentees developed relational dynamics of control over mentees' autonomy while rewarding compliance and passivity, or encouraging defiance and conflict in the mentoring bonds (Solky & Ryan, 1996; Deci et al., 1994; cf. Brumovská, 2017). This paper thus supports the argument that mentors and their approach to mentoring interactions are crucial to the quality and benefits of formal mentoring bonds (Schenk et al., 2020; Rhodes et al., 2017; Thomson & Zand, 2010; Keller & Pryce, 2010;). It revealed mentors' crucial role in applying efficient limit-setting during perceived challenges of children's behaviour encountered in mentoring interactions.

Recent progress in the field of youth mentoring has seen the development of various new mentoring schemes in the EU context, including those that primarily focus on mentors and their civic engagement, and the development of their personal and employability skills through role modelling for mentees. Following the discussion on the quality and benefits of formal youth mentoring relationships and interventions (Thomson & Zand, 2010; Bayer et al., 2015), the results of this study further suggest that the mentoring schemes should continue to focus on mentees as the primary recipients of mentoring benefits. At the same time, the benefits mentors gain by taking part in mentoring can stem from the inherent enjoyment and satisfaction they derive from the mentoring role and bond if they start volunteering with initial AMs for mentoring involvement (Brumovská & Brady, 2021) and their skills are also professionally supervised by the mentoring programme. The new mentoring schemes could thus focus on selecting mentors with initial AMs and facilitating supervision that monitors mentors' perceived mentoring efficacy, challenges and coping styles, encouraging mentoring bonds to develop with mutual relational satisfaction and related mutual benefits of the positive mentoring experience.

The results revealed the features of autonomy control in a controlling, limit-setting style of coping with perceived mentoring challenges, and related risks (Deci et al., 1994). They also revealed features of the informative limit-setting style of coping with perceived mentoring challenges that further facilitated the development of secure, high-quality mentoring bonds (cf. Brumovská, 2017). These features should be monitored and supported or mitigated accordingly during mentoring supervision and in future practice.

Prior research suggested that mentors' training, communication and the support facilitated by the mentoring scheme were significant in developing

relationship quality (DuBois et al., 2011; Kupersmidt et al., 2017; McQuillin et al., 2015; Stelter et al., 2018). This paper showed that the informative limit-setting style (Deci et al., 1994) of coping with mentees' challenging behaviour in mentoring interactions was particularly linked with features of mentors' initial autonomous motivation, willingness to honestly reflect on their mentoring skills and apply their insights with confidence during the challenging mentoring events. Supporting mentors in recognising and dealing with perceived mentoring challenges seems to be crucial to the further development and benefits of the relationships. Through specific training, mentors should be encouraged and helped to use the informative limit-setting style when coping with perceived challenges. If the professionals on the programme offer mentors support with these themes from the outset of the relationship, it will be useful good practice to develop a mentor-mentee bond with high-quality features over its span. During the supervision of formal mentors, reflection on the themes of mentoring challenges found to be common to mentors' experience – that is, accepting the mentee unconditionally without prescribed, implicit expectations; dealing with the responsibility accepted with the mentoring role, and dealing with emotional boundaries in the mentoring bond – can guide mentors towards self-reflection, awareness, honesty and authenticity in their communication, and help them develop a sense of efficacy in the mentoring role while they consciously apply their mentoring skills in the events of mentoring challenges. Continuously improving mentors' reflection, communication and relational skills will further develop their self-efficacy and minimise the risks that the autonomy-controlling mentoring approach can impose on the dynamics of the formal mentoring bonds, and on mentees as recipients of the mentoring intervention.

5. Limitations and future directions

The data of this study were collected between 2011 and 2012. The study was finished in 2017 (Brumovská, 2017). The reported data are now a decade old. This delay can mean a change in the context of similar mentoring programmes today, e. g. due to the recent experiences of a pandemic health crisis, the current war in Ukraine or new developments in the field. Nevertheless, this study addresses gaps in the literature that are still present in our knowledge on formal mentoring relationships to date. We argue that the shared themes in mentoring experiences are universal by virtue of their relational nature, and thus the theme of perceived mentoring challenges

and coping is common to all mentors' experiences. However, this theme has not been discussed in depth in the literature to date. A similar study with a qualitative in-depth longitudinal research design and focus on relational experiences and dynamics in formal youth mentoring would help identify mentoring themes in the context of the 2020s. It would compare the themes of mentoring experience reported in this study and validate whether they are shared across different contexts.

For instance, it would be beneficial for the field to research on the shared themes of relational and individual mentoring experiences across time and cultural, organisational, and social contexts to address this discussion and gaps in our knowledge in future studies.

Finally, an in-depth study on experiences of natural mentoring relationships, and how natural mentoring relationships could be further enhanced, strengthened and supported by new mentoring approaches, need to be explored in depth from a youth-centred perspective to prevent the risks of traditional formal youth mentoring schemes and better support well-being and mentoring benefits among all children and young people who can benefit from the mentoring principle.

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